

CONDITIONS OF OBSTACLES AND ENFORCEMENTS OF THE PROFESSIONAL SPORTS INDUSTRY PROMOTIONS IN THAILAND

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Abstract

The professional sports incorporates an important mainstream from the global perspective that has most of other industries within the sporting world. The sports industry in Thailand is also one of the biggest industry in the country which has social and economic development. Along with this contribution, there are various obstacles are associated with this industry. To address this issues, the current study objective was to check conditions of obstacles and enforcement for the professional sport promotion of Thailand. For this objective content qualitative analysis was done and data was collected from several journals, web sites, reports and reports related to professional sports by using a convenient and purposive sampling technique. The results shown that professional's sports industry is being gradually walked up to the industrialization along with the better growth trend as compared to other developing and developed countries, the sports industry in Thailand is still in beginning stage. The current research also described the previous obstacles which hinder the professional sports industry. And then according to these problems, the proposed enforcements to fast-track the promotion were also discussed related to professional sports industry. Thus, along with these findings this research added a body of literature from both of theoretical and empirical perspective. This research is a pioneer study which shows the obstacles and enforcement of the professional sports because the previous studies were based on specific sectors or quantitative research approach. Moreover, this study could also be a pioneer which has used the content analysis technique for analysis. In other words, the research will also help to the policy department, sports industry and also to the coaches to know about the importance of professional sports to enhance the social and also economic development.

Keywords: Sports industry, Obstacles, enforcements, Thailand

Introduction

Presently, the application of organizational and managerial duties is linked to the professional responsibilities of experts in the sphere of physical culture and sports. This highlights the importance of improving professional sports activity training in the context of player development (Martínez-Majolero, Urosa, & Hernández-Sánchez, 2022). The strategic aim of sports institutions is to design and implement novel approaches to professional training in order to develop their professional competence in a continuous, methodical, and effective manner. As a result, professional players and professionals in the field of sports need to be trained (Thomas, 2022). The demand for this specialty reflects sports professionals' desire to advance their careers in a variety of sports-related fields. This demonstrates that sports activities are valued as crucial in enhancing professional professionalism (Sukdee, 2021). The Professional Sports Commission of Thailand finally recognized and declared professional sports as a professional sport, similar to other professional vocations, after just a long delay. This official accreditation provides enterprises and players in the industry with real protection and legal requirements (Astorino, Baker, Brock, & Dalleck, 2021).

The Sports Authority of Thailand (SAT) voted in 2017 to formally authorize sports as a category of sport that can be registered as a sports association. Despite this decision, real processes and strategies for dealing with many parts of the sports sector were lacking, particularly for the protection of professional sports players' welfare and working circumstances, as it was not recognized in the same way as professional sports. Professional Sports Commission Notification re: Designation of Types or Categories of Professional Sports (sports are ultimately recognised as professional sports under the Promotion of Professional Sports Act B.E. 2556 (2013)), ("Professional Sports Act") (Khaowanna, 2021). Stakeholders inside the sports sector will be subject to the same protection and duties as pertain to traditional professional sports. This is one of the reasons why Thailand's sports sector is expanding with the passage of time. In comparison to other industries, the sports industry's revenue has increased (Kittikumpanat, 2021). In line with previous discussion, it could be seen that revenue from sports industry is being projected to reach USD152 million in 2022. The further expected revenue could be annual growth from 2022 to 2025 is 12.77 which could be resulting market volume of \$218 USD million by 2025 (Mckenzie, 2022). The average revenue from the individual user could be \$18.43 million. These contributed figures have shown that Thailand sports industry played an important role in the development of Thailand. Along with these contribution, the professionals in the sports are still on early stages due to the mismanagement of resources and still had limited literature on sports industry of Thailand (JANSUKWONG & Sungkawadee, 2022).

Keeping the importance of Thailand sports for professionals, the previous researches still have some gaps. For instance, the research in the fields of sports were mainly accompanied on the developed nations (Mckenzie, 2022) while had limited attention on the developing nations such as Thailand land sports (PWC, 2021) which had various obstacles in the development of professional behavior in the sports industry. It was argued the various issues associated with the such as sports industry is doping and the adverse publicity is being causes, the pressures is on individuals to perform better, the withdrawals of the fund suddenly from the sports industry and financial viability of professional team and sports club (PWC, 2021). There are various other obstacles which are associated along with sports professionals. Therefore, the current study purpose is to check those obstacles and enforcement of professional sports of Thailand. Despite the fact that Thailand's professional sports industry (PSI) is quickly growing, there's few associated studies. Furthermore, the studies mostly mentioned the situation and provided growth plans in part, while only a few methodically outlined current barriers to the implementation of the PSI and recommended full solutions. To solve this issue, we thoroughly assess its challenges in this article and do their best in suggest effective ways from businesses, government, as well as society based on the current scenario in Thailand.

Research Methodology

The investigation was based on content analysis qualitative research. Content analysis is a methodology for determining the existence of specific words, topics, or concepts in qualitative data (X. Xie, Huo, & Zou, 2019). Researchers can quantify and analyses the presence, meanings, and relationships of specific words, themes, or concepts using content analysis

(Lindgren, Lundman, & Graneheim, 2020). Researchers, for example, can assess the language used in a news story to look for prejudice or partiality. Scholars could then deduce information about the documents' messages, the researcher, the audience, and even the culture and time period in which the text was written. Interviews, open-ended inquiries, field study notes, dialogues, or literally any occurrence of communicative language could be used as data sources (such as books, essays, discussions, newspaper headlines, speeches, media, historical documents) (Roller, 2019). As a result, the researcher in this study collected data for the research objective using secondary sources such as reports, articles, websites, and other secondary sources.

Research Findings

The research findings consists of two phases. In first it was seen about the obstacles which are associated with the sports professionals and in other phase it was found the enforcements for the sports professionals.

Obstacles for Thailand's Professional sports industry

As a growing sector in Thailand, PSI are beset with challenges, with a slew of issues surfacing as the industry grows. Under this article, we primarily study and determine such issues as they relate to themselves, businesses, society, and civilization.

Internal Obstacles for professional Sports Industry

The PSI grew in Thailand as in 1990s, but despite its fast expansion over three decades, this is still undeveloped and with its infancy. Overall investment in the sports business remains usually minimal, with sports-related investments accounting for barely 0.1 % investment in the country. Because of the low investment, the sports industry's production only accounts for a modest percentage of GDP. Most of this demonstrates that Thailand's sports business is still lagging behind (Srimuk, Suanpang, & Netwong, 2021). As per statistical data, Thailand's sports business performance taken into account for just 0.3 percent of Gross domestic product in 1999, whereas Switzerland's sports industry production recorded 3.37 percent, Germany's 1.25 percent, Spain's 1.68 percent, the United Kingdom's 1.56 percent, and Finland's 1.70 percent, that were significantly greater than our country's. Furthermore, Thailand's sports population is significantly lower than that of industrialized countries, accounting for only 31.2 % population (Sukdee, 2021).

Because of High population, every capita stadium capacity is unquestionably restricted. Thailand's PSI growth seems comparable to that of most industrialized nations in the early twentieth century, despite the fact that it is still a developing country. Furthermore, a Chinese government prioritized the growth of competitive sports, resulting in less investment in the PSI, putting the PSI in a precarious position in its development. Whereas the PSI grew in importance over time, the Chinese government provided less support, falling behind its development. Undoubtedly, the PSI is still in its early stages of development. It is just an emerging industry in comparison to industrialized nations, necessitating greater investigation

of economic consequences on economic and social development (Teeranuwat & Thithathan, 2021).

Irrational Structure

With terms of features, the PSI encompasses a wide range of activities; unfortunately, the growth of each subcategory of the PSI has been unpredictable. For starters, sports as part of the entertainment sector remain a major player in the PSI. These have developed the market pattern in which multiple investment issues coexist, and primary and secondary sports service items compete. Their service products, rates, as well as service features rapidly gained public acceptance, resulting in a universal, diversified tendency. Nevertheless, the Sports Fitness Industry remains still in its infancy, with a poor service quality and minimal consumer interest. In general, it is not grown, except perhaps in the initial phases of development. Second, despite its early beginnings, the athletic goods business was rather mature. In 2008, there were approximately 4 million sporting goods enterprises, with 25000 of them operating on a large scale (Adheli, 2020). More than half of Thailand's sports business actual output is based on the fast expansion of the sport goods sector; nowadays, over than % of sports equipment are manufactured in Thailand, Jiang and Lin (2014) indicating that its development of Thailand's sport market for goods and services has achieved some progress (Chroni, Medgard, Nilsen, Sigurjónsson, & Solbakken, 2018).

On the other hand, several issues were revealed, including low-technology items, additional low-end products, a resulting loss of high-end product lines, fewer own-brand products, limited ability for modernize products, less development of innovative sporting goods, as well as a greater supply of old OEM products. The performance of spectator sports and competitive shows has advanced significantly. The market for comprehensive tournaments and numerous sports events has slowly grown. These sectors have made extensive use of market expansion methods such as level sponsorship, delegated sponsorship, special rights, and broadcast television rights. Consequently, Thailand's competitive performance was hampered by poor market participant expansion, insufficient development and exploitation of event facilities, and semi event market management, making it difficult to establish a professional racing identity comparable to the NBA. The PSI process looks to be illogical, with the primary business falling behind and no intermediary industry (Adheli, 2020). When looking at the country as a whole, the competitive performance business is growing quickly, whereas the core industries like sports inside this "entertainment, service, tourist, and media industries" are growing slowly. Furthermore, there seems to be a gap in the market for intermediary industries, including professional sports employment or technology. In addition, there is a lack of connectivity between the multiple areas, trying to establish a considerable scale, much alone an entire industrial system.

Uneven Region Development

The topic of unbalanced regional PSI growth in Thailand is currently quite prominent. Because of the significant differences in regional economic growth, particularly eastern, southern, and northern coastal areas have unique benefits inside this establishment of PSI in terms of software

over the Midwest and other interior locations. In the PSI, there is clearly a gradient of growth in the East, the Middle, and the West. Its rise of "Beijing and Tianjin as the hub of the Bohai Bay economic circle, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, and Shanghai as the center of the Yangtze River Delta economic circle, and Guangzhou and Shenzhen as the center of the Pearl River Delta economic circle is especially noteworthy" (Williams, Kim, & Nauright, 2021). Customers demand for professional sports was higher in such regions, the PSI began slightly earlier within those sectors, there's more casual organizations, and standard of service as well as customer satisfaction remain also significantly greater, all of which contributed to a fast growth momentum, whereas the Midwest was in its infancy, despite these positive development. There is an imbalance in the PSI across areas, and similarly, there will be an imbalance among cities, with first-tier areas having a greater degree of PSI growth than second-tier regions and other ordinary cities. Additionally, there is an imbalance across urban to rural regions; the degree of growth of city's PSI is significantly higher than either rural areas, or urban citizens are becoming the primary consumers of PSI. The issue of a major regional imbalance in the PSI is strongly tied to the growth of Thailand's local economic inequalities (Williams et al., 2021).

Professional Sports Enterprises Defect

Lack of operational professionals and deprived operational efficiency

Though the organized economy's influence is concerned, Thailand's sports endeavors have been dedicated to the public good, and state intervention seems to have become weather vanes in formulating sports development strategies. The existing system in Thailand has still been centered on sports can set up and arrange resources, and the lack of response to customer demands of professional sports divides the interoperability between sports as well as the sports sector inside the development cycle to some extent. Because of government action, businesses lack adequate autonomy inside this course of its operations. As a result, any associated business strategy has fallen behind, and proper market orientation or innovation strategy is no longer possible. PSI firms employed an outmoded way of organization, controlling the components of a singular, as well as advertising methods that had fallen behind and innovation that would have been lacking, making it extremely difficult to fulfil consumer expectations and demands when participating in sports activities. Simultaneously, a scarcity of operational experts has hampered the PSI growth. It is challenging for operational professionals in the PSI in Thailand to attain the needed level of quality or quantity in the PSI (The Ministry of Tourism and Sports Thailand, 2022). Nowadays, the majority of sports management teams seem to be athletes as well as coaches who, while possessing a certain degree of fitness ability, complete absence knowledge of strategic management and marketing capabilities, as well as an awareness of market operating and economic wealth, finding it tough to develop and market sports goods and services to customers. However, many investors and entrepreneurs were familiar to operational abilities but lack comprehension of market characteristics and market norms connected in professional sports as well as their goods, making it difficult to integrate professional sports to market-oriented operations. Presented with the present competitive marketplace, one of the obstacles limiting the growth of the PSI in Thailand was a dearth of operating experts in the PSI (The Ministry of Tourism and Sports Thailand, 2022).

The Obstacles in the Government and Social Supports

The Misallocation of professional Sports Source through the Government

Despite the fact that the government has developed numerous PSI in various cities and has supplied sports exercise classes across our countries, those who are still unable to fulfil public demand. As per data, just 44.1 percent of stadiums are fully open, 21.3 percent are half-open and 34.6 percent are not open (The Ministry of Tourism and Sports Thailand, 2022). Furthermore, the professional sports capacity must be utilized. Thailand is a multicultural country with a wide area and abundant natural resources; every country will have its own sociocultural characteristics (The Ministry of Tourism and Sports Thailand, 2022). When these factors are determined and utilized wisely. Professional sports would be plentiful, eliminating signal markets, a shortage of inventiveness, and uniqueness.

Lack of the Synergistic Push Mechanism

Instead of being a self-contained business, the PSI remain a system engineering who enables and collaborates with certain other enterprises, including a wide range of upstream and downstream industries and sectors, including education, tourist, economic, medical, protection, and culture. As a result, in preferring to pay more attention on its own growth, the PSI needs collaborative development with other departments to accomplish quick growth. Although our country has relied on the hot expenditure of the holiday economy for fuel domestic consumption in latest days, industrial development has been disrupted. Catering disasters, heavy traffic, and insufficient service are difficult to resolve; education and findings in the PSI are relatively limited, despite significant investment in education, resulting in misunderstanding with in PSI; professional sports and amusement initiatives insufficient innovation and are classified by nonstandard administration and performance. Furthermore, due to our nation's lack of healthcare monitoring, researchers are unable to conduct frequent inspections as well as physical examinations of participants, resulting in a paucity of scientific data on people participating following initial body-building workouts. Overall, we still need a framework that takes into account as whole and planning purposes in order to encourage the growth of the PSI (Sukdee, 2021).

Low Standard of Market and Defective Market Systems

The industry is still in disarray, and the acceptable level is not sufficient, because PSI in our nation was in its infancy. Due to the reduced obstacles to entry in PSI, an influx of investors has flooded the market, resulting in market saturation throughout many areas and increased competitiveness. Utilizing price like a selling factor, on the other hand, prevents market standardization as well as fair growth; many businessmen utilize unfair competitive tactics to maintain their own privileged position, gravely weakening market order. Such occurred primarily as a result of the development of a supervisory framework, and a lack of oversight and relating to the administration on the component of business groups. Furthermore, regulations governing PSI are not flawless, with poor legislative standards, an unformed legal structure, and an absence on systematism and completeness, and they are unable to keep up

with the industry's rapid growth. Like a consequence, the proper implementation of a limitation mechanism is becoming a critical and effective incentive for the growth of PSI (Boonchutima, Sukonthasab, & Sthapitanonda, 2020).

Enforcement Analysis on Professional sports industry in Thailand

However the PSI in our nation has demonstrated a quick growth trend and a promising future, it has also revealed a number of issues that are substantially hindering its progress. The study will pay more attention on the policies that will drive its development after analyzing its current challenges.

Policies from Government Respect

Professional sports industry Financing Policies

Improving and polishing business and investment strategies is critical to attaining the objective of a healthy and long-term growth of PSI. Undoubtedly, establishing solid PSI investment as well as finance regulations is critical to the growth of the PSI in our nation right now. With the simultaneous concept that government as well as society investment moves hand in hand, researchers must broaden direct connections to financing and investment, implement a percentage of policy measures to inspire society investment, and therefore create a favorable environment with pluralism investing and financing strategies (Geraplansub & Gultawatvichai, 2019). In particular, stimulate society's investment in PSI; make sports administration institutes and organizations free from restrictions for non-public economic factors or non-sports system involvement. Secondly, promote formation of the sports investment businesses and competitive sports assets, as well as the conversion of investment bodies between individual governments towards corporations, non-profits, social organizations, and the general public (Chancharat & Meeprom, 2021). To develop diversified investment organizations and modes, increase the investment mode out of a particular government fund towards diverse financing ways including sports lottery, sport securities, and sports funds. Third, provide limited loans and interest rebates for innovative sports business initiatives, and also stimulate and develop the PSI through policy loans (Somphong, 2020b).

Industry structure optimization and enforcement connections development within industries

Optimizing market position, implementing reasonable changes with industrial architecture at the same time, and fostering industry connection creation are all critical to the PSI overall development. To begin, fundamental industries such as fitness as well as leisure, and the function business, must be prioritized in terms of optimizing industry structure (Sutthichaimethee & Naluang, 2019). By cultivating, growing, and upgrading such essential element, the entire industry may be modified and streamlined. Second, we must vigorously promote its intermediary market, consequently to pay more attention on the key industries. Inside of our nation, the PSI remains in its early stages (Thummajariyawat, 2018). As a result, need in sports intermediary services will continue to develop, indicating a dynamic scenario. Furthermore, because our country is so large, each area does have its own culture and assets.

Like a consequence, each region must build PSI that represents their particular cultural identities and is based on relative advantages. Likewise, the regional government must establish an internal economic link and mixture between the PSI and its connected industries in the growth process, mobilize the significant improvement of linked businesses together, and integrate PSI with local economy through development, organically integrate PSI to enhance regional ability to compete (Sutthichaimethee, 2019).

Promoting Professional Education of sports, and strengthening professional sports industry Management Personnel

The PSI must depend on skilled management to expand steadily and methodically in its processes. As a result, our government can promote professional sports education as well as management training, and also maintain a steady supply of skilled manpower. To drastically handle the issue of PSI shortage of experts, the public and government must implement a number of educational measures (Ibay & Pa-alisbo, 2020). These following are the specifics: Firstly, establish a high-level sports economy degree by opening professions and courses in PSI at public high universities or sports colleges, Students will be taught sound management theory, given training chances to mix theoretical concepts, and would be in an all-round growth phase. Furthermore, create appropriate research organizations, strengthen research, improve and deepen concept, create an effective research guidance system, and provide timely advice on practice. Finally, motivate employees in PSI to continue professional work training and future education, improve service, as well as train more business experts in step with the sector's growth (Varothai & Bunchapattanasakda, 2020).

Regulating about the Environment of Market, and Attaining the Authorization Improvement on professional Sports Industry

Our nation's PSI is now unstable, disorganized, and devoid of a regulatory framework, all of which obstruct their development. Many issues in a market economy could be handled through spontaneous economic forces, while others require applicable legislation to be managed. To ensure a normative PSI atmosphere and attain authorization of the recreational sports sector, the government should establish correlating initiatives, enhance applicable legal documents, and implement some supervision or restrictions mechanisms. Legalization of the PSI is the only way to ensure that it develops in a healthy, organized, and normative manner (Geddie, 2019; Terason, 2018). Presently, state-enacted sports industry rules seem to be mostly complete management methodologies, not particular and respectful for every relationship and sport, as well as complete absence flexibility in the project implementation; such as, a few sports initiatives nevertheless implement to sociocultural and professional sports controlled and manipulated. Furthermore, the PSI still a growing industry within our nation, and the growth of sports industries was in its early stages of the investigation, with no applicable regulatory mechanisms in place (Das, 2021; Geddie, 2019).

As an outcome, the government needs to develop market management standards and policies in the PSI that are aligned with sports law, actually identifying the rights, obligations, and duties of investors, funders, management staff, organizations, and nongovernmental

organizations in the sports industry, rely on legislation and rules to secure PSI, and enjoy the benefits of laws to combat and punish infringement activities (Das, 2021). Hence, to effectively manage the PSI and maintain its healthy growth, adhere to all applicable rules and regulations.

The Policies for the Enterprises

Industrial Development and professional Sports Industry

The PSI is intertwined with other sectors like tourism, media, production, and insurance. With the line in this, businesses may combine application context based on the relevance of PSI, collaboratively grow, and increase their operations (C. Xie & Shen, 2021). Encourage the development of recreational sports tourist items. Sports tourism isn't just a type of tourism; it's also a new area that combines sports with tourism. Sport tourism may be enhanced through developing professional sports organizations and resorts that encourage travelers to participate in recreational activities while on vacation. Numerous travel agencies are realized the commercial opportunities created with the tourist and sports industries' mutual penetration, and that is also fulfil consumer expectations and support the growth of sports media, positively exploit different types of sport tourist goods surrounding important sport events at domestically and overseas, sports education, sports interaction, as well as sports watch (Yu & Medvid, 2021). The sports media sector is an important sector having significant profitability and quick growth. Companies can engage with big television networks to develop and extend their sports media operations. However the sports sector has been on the increase, it's now inside its infancy, with plenty of room for expansion. It will undoubtedly expand swiftly if we would successfully integrate and utilize sports or other associated businesses, and also widen the PSI Company (Klinsrisuk & Pechdin, 2022).

Modernizing the philosophy of business and improved economic benefits

Nowadays, the PSI mentality is falling behind. Enterprise struggles to match most customers' needs and demands when they participate in PSI because of hazy marketing strategy, archaic operating methods, limited products, outdated market methods, and inadequate innovation. As a result, businesses must rapidly reinvent their mindset and build a market in a diverse range of products (Thongrawd, Bootpo, Thipha, & Jermisittiparsert, 2019). The following are some noteworthy examples of the worldwide professional sports industry: first, establish clear marketing strategy, take advantage, structure, and enhance product offerings, like ski resorts as well as rafting resorts; second, present the idea of franchising, such as outdoor activities, diving, and club; and third, intensify goods linked and chain sales, including such establishing structure fitness clubs. Simultaneously, businesses must assess the elements that impact their performance, and also research and implement the best marketing strategy and methods. To fierce competition, these same traditional four dimensions, notably product, cost of production, placement, and advertisement, has failed to fulfill customers' needs and desires. Rather than, businesses must incorporate modern humanities, ecofriendly marketing of specific features, and other advanced ideas to fulfil customers' needs and wants (Thongrawd et al., 2019). Furthermore, businesses must increase their innovation, establish new and innovative products and initiatives, and improve product innovation, particularly for industrial companies on whom

the products seem to be primarily limited and small, despite the fact that they are unable to possess the rising market with high efficiency and an absence of adequate support. As a conclusion, improving R&d efforts and innovation not only enhances the company's benefits, and also improves it compete (Somphong, 2020a).

Growing Marketing and Constructing Brands through Its Particular Characteristics

Because of a shortage of specialists, the abilities in promotional campaigns, marketing, especially brand strategy are exceedingly inadequate when compared to advance PSI abroad. As a result, businesses must create their own distinctive brand, increase marketing efforts, and raise brand recognition, all while concentrating on enhancing services and goods. PSI provides individuals with not only a delightful experience, and therefore a cultural learning and communication process. After that, by integrating professional's sports cultural heritage to fashion, businesses must put an emphasis upon this inheritance and expansion of PSI, and construct their own promotional strategies and placement. To establish a good brand effect, businesses must develop detailed marketing campaigns, commercialize their brands through multiple media marketing, press conferences, as well as sponsorship of famous sporting events, and built a strong impression through getting involved in big public welfare for the purpose of build brand awareness. The performance of the 2008 Olympic Games and the 2010 Asian Games, for instance, is not a chance to proliferate and advance on the global stage (Somphong, 2020a).

Social aspect Policies

Polices on the development of sports association

Numerous sports organizations are now engaged in the creation of sports in Thailand. Whereas in control of a wide range of professional activities, sports organizations need to focus more on popularizing every sport within the organization, as well as managing different professional sports exercise classes using scientific rising popularity and methodologies, which will not only enhances the performance of professional sporting events, and also deepen their multi-understanding, speed up their popularization, and enhance skills and experience in management and operation (Foopanichpruk & Pathranarakul, 2022). Often these sports organizations in our region were also governed through the government; as a result, sports organizations should take proactive steps to improve their activities and performance, such as interacting and collaborating with innovative organizations with extensive experience in other countries through cross-cultural communication (Santirojanakul, 2018). Enhancing sports organizations boosts the popularization of professional sports and activities, hence encouraging the PSI development (Somphong & Rattamanee, 2019).

Revolution from the Community Sports Management System for the Public Oriented System

According to Suebmai, Karnjanakit, and Gulthawatvichai (2019) community sports seem to be the foundation underlying national sports growth as well as the building blocks for professional sports. Inside of our state, the community sports control system remains government-

oriented; modern sports method still prioritizes competitive sports when establishing establishments and allocating resources, ignoring the requirement for professional sports. With some significant degree, the above differentiates sports as from sports industry, making it simple to stifle the PSI growth. As an outcome, community sports must transition from a government-oriented toward a public-oriented management structure, allowing more citizens to engage with grassroots sports or participate in professional sports and activities based on individual preferences and hobbies (Naraine & Wanless, 2020). Such unquestionably pique people's interest while also providing benefits for boost demand for PSI. We could enforce two components to modify into a public-oriented control system: next, startup professional sports activities, which entails establishing up a large organizational structure from roads to community as well as family, and frequently coordinating residents to engage students in learning for local neighborhood unity through mobilizing public engagement. Afterwards, create civil society groups, which will form a network in which the local sports organization will be in responsible for overall jurisdiction, but every company will be mutually independent (Jedaman, Buaraphan, Pimvichai, Yuenyong, & Jeerasombat, 2019). Every group conducts its activities independently, with just minor assistance provided as essential. As a result, it is advantageous to publicize professional sports and to encourage their development.

Conclusions

The study objective was to check the Conditions of Obstacles and Enforcement of the Professional Sports in Thailand. For this purpose, the secondary data qualitative content analysis was done. The key has shown that Thailand's professional industry is still inside of its infancy, experiencing several challenges and stresses, it also has a lot of room for growth by assessing current challenges and implementing the strategies identified in this study. Well with advancement of social and economic life, as well as the enhancement of living, we think it would become a cornerstone business that will drive Thailand's economy forward for the coming years, and an unavoidable consumer trend. Thus, along with these findings this research added a body of literature from both of theoretical and empirical perspective. This research is a pioneer study which shows the obstacles and enforcement of the professional sports because the previous studies were based on specific sectors or quantitative research approach. Moreover, this study could also be a pioneer which has used the content analysis technique for analysis. In other words, the research will also help to the policy department, sports industry and also to the coaches to know about the importance of professional sports to enhance the social and also economic development. The study was also have several limitations. The study was limited on qualitative research design and future research could be explored along with both of qualitative and quantitative mixed research approach to know about the research results variations. The study was also limited on Thailand nations, the further research could be done on other countries to know about the results variations.

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